

The Missing Thread: Integrating Textiles into Australia's National Waste Policy for a Circular Future

Renay Wells

Griffith University

Abstract

Textile waste remains one of the fastest growing waste streams globally, yet Australia's National Waste Policy Action Plan (NWPAP) notably omits textiles from its core targets. This omission highlights a critical governance gap that undermines progress toward circular economy transitions and sustainable consumption and production (SCP) goals. While plastics, food, and e-waste receive dedicated policy attention, the absence of textiles perpetuates a system in which fast fashion externalities—ranging from landfill dependency to microplastic pollution—remain unregulated and underestimated. This paper critically examines the implications of this policy blind spot, situating it within broader debates on extended producer responsibility (EPR), co-regulation, and stewardship schemes such as the Australian Fashion Council's Seamless Clothing Stewardship Scheme. Drawing on national policy analysis and global best practice, it argues that integrating textiles into formal waste strategies is essential for aligning Australia's governance frameworks with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). Addressing the missing thread within the NWPAP is not only a matter of waste management, but a prerequisite for systemic reform toward a truly circular and sustainable fashion industry.

Keywords: Textile Waste; National Waste Policy Action Plan (NWPAP); Circular Economy (CE); Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP); Fashion Industry; Textile; Sustainability; Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR); Waste Governance; Stewardship Schemes; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Australia.

Introduction:

The Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW), in releasing the *National Waste Policy Action Plan 2019* (NWPAP), failed to define and regulate the growing social and environmental problem of textile waste. While the plan addressed plastics, food, and e-waste, its silence on fashion and textiles left a critical gap in Australia's waste governance. This omission has significant implications: fashion oversupply and consumer excess continue to drive a mounting waste stream, with synthetic textiles in particular posing acute ecological risks through landfill dependency, microplastic pollution, and hazardous leachates. The policy's limited definition of "waste" reflects a

broader governance challenge—without comprehensive categorisation, major issues such as textile waste remain invisible and unaddressed.

This paper argues that the exclusion of textiles from the NWPAP exemplifies a deeper policy-implementation gap, where the political credit for announcing legislation outweighs the effort required to address complex systemic problems (Hudson et al., 2019). To explore this gap, the analysis is structured in three parts. **Part A** defines the policy problem, examining the scale and characteristics of textile waste. **Part A.1** considers potential solutions through extended producer responsibility (EPR), stewardship schemes, and circular economy principles. **Part A.2** evaluates the factors shaping the policy process, including competing interests, governance capacity, and industry resistance. Finally, **Part B** highlights the importance of precise problem definition in policy design, showing how the framing of “waste” directly influences whether textiles are regulated or neglected.

By situating textile waste within this policy framework, the paper demonstrates how governance gaps in Australia’s waste strategy not only perpetuate environmental harm but also hinder progress toward circular economy transitions and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Part A. Defining the policy problem

The *National Waste Policy Action Plan 2019* (NWPAP), agreed upon by all Australian governments, established seven targets and actions intended to guide national investment. To support these objectives and underpin the waste export ban, the Commonwealth committed \$190 million through the Recycling Modernisation Fund, with additional capital provided by state and territory governments (DCCEEW, 2019). While these commitments represent a significant policy intervention, the absence of a clear definition of waste that explicitly includes textiles reveals a fundamental shortcoming in the plan’s design.

Policy scholarship highlights that “faulty policy design can stem from many causes: a poor understanding of the problem; insufficient knowledge of the implementation context; unclear and even contradictory goals; poor quality evidence; and an absence of political backing” (Hudson et al., 2019). The exclusion of textiles reflects precisely these conditions, suggesting either a lack of understanding of the magnitude of textile waste or an unwillingness to address the politically sensitive dimensions of fashion consumption and disposal.

Moreover, the failure to incorporate a broad spectrum of stakeholders—including textile producers, fashion retailers, and waste management organisations—during the policy formulation stage contributed to an inadequate framing of the problem. As a result, responsibility for addressing the systemic impacts of textile waste, such as the growing

presence of garments in landfill both domestically and through offshore dumping, has been displaced onto external actors. This displacement is evident in the reliance on industry-led initiatives such as the *National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme* (NCPSS), which attempts to fill the governance gap left by the NWPAP.

Part A.1. Finding Solutions to Policy Problems:

In response to growing concerns about waste governance, an inquiry into *Australia's Waste Management and Recycling Industry* was conducted in 2020, with submissions from key actors such as the Australian Academy of Technology and Engineering (ATSE). This process reflected a co-regulatory approach, in which industry develops and administers its own frameworks, while government provides the legislative infrastructure to ensure compliance. Although co-regulation offers potential efficiencies, it also risks privileging industry-led interests over public accountability, particularly in sectors like textiles where voluntary initiatives have historically underperformed.

Charitable Recycling Australia's *National Textiles Reuse Policy* (2020) was one of the first significant attempts to address this policy gap. Its recommendations—investment in national data collection, prioritisation of reuse in government policy, support for market initiatives, and public education—demonstrated an integrated vision for a circular economy. However, the fact that such proposals originated outside formal government strategy underscores the absence of a proactive federal stance.

Momentum continued with the House of Representatives Standing Committee's report *From Rubbish to Resources: Building a Circular Economy* (2020), which identified systemic waste challenges but again failed to foreground textiles. This omission reinforced a recurring policy blind spot: textiles are consistently treated as peripheral, despite their significant ecological footprint.

A more targeted intervention occurred through the 2021 National Textile Waste Roundtable, which convened industry and community actors to push for a measurable, outcome-oriented action plan. Its influence contributed to clothing textiles being placed on the Minister's Priority List for 2021–22. As shown in Table 1, the Priority List identified four actions spanning product design, stewardship schemes, baseline data collection, and lifecycle impact reduction, with timelines extending to 2025. While symbolically important, these actions were not backed by enforceable mandates or substantial federal funding. As such, they risk operating more as agenda-setting devices than transformative levers for systemic change.

Class of products	Year first listed:	Reasons for inclusion:	Actions recommended:	Timing for action:
Clothing textiles	2021 - 2022	Textiles include clothing, carpets, furniture coverings, rags, bags, and tarpaulins. For the purposes of this list, the scope of textiles is limited to clothing. In 2018–19 Australia generated 780,000 tonnes of textile waste, with clothing comprising roughly 39 per cent by weight. Only 7 per cent was recycled with the remaining going to landfill. In 2019–20, Australia exported 47,300 tonnes of textile waste (mostly worn clothing). No formal collection services for reused textiles, with collection borne mainly by charities.	ACTION 1: Industry should take action to reduce the volume of clothing being sent to landfill. A focus should be the design and production of goods that facilitate longevity and reuse.	2022 - 2025
			ACTION 2: Design a national product stewardship scheme for end-of-life uniforms and workwear.	June 2022
			ACTION 3: Set up an industry wide stakeholder group to establish baseline data for material flows of various categories of textiles and drive action on textiles.	June 2022 (This could include for example increasing recycling potential, material flows data and reporting, research and development, product design to reduce waste and facilitate reuse and recycling).
			ACTION 4: Manufacturers, importers, distributors, and retailers should reduce the environmental impacts of clothing across the lifecycle including through product design improvements related to durability, reparability, re-usability and/or recyclability of clothing.	2025

Table 1. Minister's Priority List for Clothing Textiles (2021–2025): Actions and Timelines

Part A.2. Problems Shaping the Policy Process:

Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham (2019) emphasise that many implementation difficulties arise not from weak intentions, but from complications in the formulation and early development of policy. These challenges often stem from “the weakness of collaborative policymaking and the failure to establish a common ground for public problem-solving through a constructive management of difference” (p. 3). In the case of textile waste, the absence of consensus across government portfolios, industry actors, and civil society groups has shaped a policy process in which fragmentation and omission are recurring outcomes.

While external stakeholders have played an important role in framing textile waste as a pressing social and environmental issue, sustained government recognition remains fundamental. The creation of the National Product Stewardship Fund, with a \$1 million grant allocated as seed funding for textile initiatives, represents an acknowledgment of the problem. However, the modest scale of this intervention raises questions about whether it reflects substantive policy commitment or symbolic recognition of advocacy pressures.

Ross and Dovers (2008) identify three reasons why integrating environmental concerns into policy is particularly difficult: it runs counter to the entrenched specialisation of

public administration; it intersects with a wide range of social, economic, and resource sectors; and it is housed within government portfolios that are institutionally weak and politically marginal. These dynamics are evident in the NWPAP's treatment of textiles. Despite evidence of escalating textile waste volumes, the environment portfolio lacked the political influence to expand the policy definition of waste, resulting in textiles being sidelined relative to plastics and e-waste.

The slow integration of textile considerations also reflects deficiencies in policy impact analysis. As noted by the Office of Impact Analysis (2023), rigorous impact assessment is essential for ensuring that policies are evidence-based and aligned with long-term sustainability goals. Yet in the case of the NWPAP, the absence of impact modelling for textile waste contributed to narrow definitions and weak institutional mechanisms for reform.

Moreover, Clemons and McBeth (2020) remind us that policy processes are iterative and shaped by competing narratives. The dominant narrative surrounding the NWPAP framed waste in terms of high-visibility streams such as plastics, while rendering textiles less politically salient. This narrative imbalance continues to influence how responsibilities are delegated, with schemes such as the National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme (NCPSS) carrying much of the burden for addressing textile waste despite limited statutory authority.

Ultimately, the problems shaping the NWPAP reflect a combination of fragmented governance, weak policy integration, and underdeveloped impact analysis. Indeed, the Australian National Audit Office (ANAO, 2022) reinforced these concerns by documenting shortcomings in the federal government's own implementation of the NWPAP, highlighting a persistent gap between policy ambition and delivery performance. These structural features constrain Australia's capacity to embed textiles into its circular economy agenda, perpetuating a governance gap that requires urgent redress if national and international sustainability commitments are to be met.

Part B. The Importance of Problem Definition:

Clemons and McBeth (2020) argue that problem definition is arguably the most crucial step in policy analysis, highlighting its inherently subjective and contested nature. They stress the centrality of language, narratives, and framing in shaping how issues are constructed and prioritised. In the case of the NWPAP, the absence of explicit recognition of textiles reflects how selective framing of the "waste problem" narrowed the scope of action, privileging more visible waste streams such as plastics and food over less politically salient but equally damaging textile flows.

Kay (2011) connects this issue to the broader ends–means model of policymaking, which separates policy instruments (means) from objectives (ends). He argues that evidence-based policymaking has the potential to overcome some of the limitations of politicised decision-making. Yet in the case of the NWPAP, insufficient evidence gathering and weak analytical frameworks contributed to an incomplete problem definition. Without robust data on textile flows and impacts, policymakers were unable—or unwilling—to align policy instruments with the broader sustainability objectives embedded in national and international commitments.

Schneider and Ingram (2017) similarly note that when policy problems are framed instrumentally and narrowly, compromises and negotiations risk producing only partial or symbolic solutions. This was evident in the way textiles were initially omitted from the NWPAP, only to later reappear on the Minister’s Priority List through external advocacy. Such reactive adjustments demonstrate how weak problem definition can lead to fragmented policy responses rather than comprehensive reform.

Stone’s (2002) assertion that “problem definition is a matter of representation” is particularly salient here. The portrayal of textiles as peripheral or outside the immediate waste policy frame delayed serious attention to their impacts. This raises a critical question: did textiles only become a “problem” once industry actors and advocacy groups mobilised evidence of harm, or did policymakers within DCCEEW fail to recognise the issue due to institutional blind spots and competing political priorities?

Ultimately, the case of textiles in the NWPAP illustrates that how a problem is defined shapes the boundaries of possible solutions. A mixed-methods approach—integrating quantitative evidence of waste flows with qualitative insights from industry, charities, and consumers—could have enabled a more holistic and durable definition of the problem. Instead, the absence of such an approach left responsibility displaced onto the National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme (NCPSS), perpetuating the risks of fragmented and insufficient action.

Conclusion:

The omission of textiles from Australia’s National Waste Policy Action Plan (2019) exemplifies the consequences of weak problem definition. By failing to recognise textiles as a distinct and urgent waste stream, policymakers constrained the scope of possible interventions and left responsibility fragmented across industry-led initiatives. The displacement of accountability onto schemes such as the National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme (NCPSS) demonstrates how governance gaps emerge when systemic problems are excluded at the agenda-setting stage. This critique is consistent with findings

from the Australian National Audit Office (ANAO, 2022), which identified weaknesses in the federal government’s delivery of the NWPAP, underscoring the broader pattern of implementation failure that continues to marginalise textiles within national waste policy.

This case highlights the centrality of problem definition to effective policy. As Clemons and McBeth (2020) argue, the framing of an issue shapes not only its perceived legitimacy but also the policy instruments deployed in response. In the NWPAP, the dominance of plastics and e-waste as politically visible categories marginalised textiles, despite mounting evidence of their environmental and social impacts. A mixed-methods approach—integrating robust data on textile flows with the lived realities of industry, community organisations, and consumers—could have delivered a more comprehensive framework and pre-empted the current reliance on piecemeal solutions.

Moving forward, integrating textiles into national waste strategies is not simply a matter of technical adjustment; it is a question of governance, equity, and systemic reform. Effective stewardship will require mandatory producer responsibility, enforceable targets, and sustained investment in circular infrastructure, supported by transparent monitoring and public accountability. Without this, Australia risks perpetuating a cycle of symbolic commitments that fall short of substantive change.

Addressing this “missing thread” is therefore not only a matter of waste management, but a prerequisite for systemic reform capable of shifting the fashion industry toward a circular and sustainable future.

References:

- Australian Academy of Technology and Engineering. (2020, January). *Submission to inquiry into Australia's waste management and recycling industries*. <https://www.atse.org.au/research-and-policy/publications/publication/submission-to-inquiry-into-australias-waste-management-and-recycling-industries/>.
- Australian Fashion Council. (2023, February 23). *National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme*. <https://ausfashioncouncil.com/program/product-stewardship/>.
- Australian Fashion Council. (2023). *NCPSS data report*. Australian Fashion Council. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KjX6pRsPI9WPjFW1ANJXz0o4XNyigoCB/view>.
- Australian Government. (2020, December 17). *Recycling and Waste Reduction Act 2020*. Federal Register of Legislation. <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2020A00119>.
- Australian Parliament House. (2023). *House Standing Committee on Industry, Science and Resources*. Parliament of Australia. Retrieved 21 April, 2023, from https://www.aph.gov.au/Parliamentary_Business/Committees/House/Industry_Science_and_Resources.
- Clemons, R. S., & McBeth, M. K. (2020). In *Public Policy Praxis: A Case Approach for Understanding Policy and Analysis* (pp. 211–260). essay, Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Commonwealth of Australia. (2022). *Australian government implementation of the National Waste Policy Action Plan: Australian National Audit Office (ANAO)*. Australian National Audit Office (ANAO). Retrieved March 29, 2023, from <https://www.anao.gov.au/work/performance-audit/australian-government-implementation-the-national-waste-policy-action-plan>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. (2021, October 3). *Product stewardship in Australia*. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste/product-stewardship>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. (2022, October 21). *Clothing textiles*. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste/product-stewardship/textile-waste-roundtable>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. (2022, October 26). *Minister's priority list 2021–22*. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste/product-stewardship/ministers-priority-list/2021-22>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. (2022, November 17). *Waste and recycling*. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water. (2022, December 9). *National Waste Policy Action Plan*. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/waste/publications/national-waste-policy-action-plan>.
- Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet. (2023, March). *Australian government guide to policy impact analysis*. Office of Impact Analysis. <https://oia.pmc.gov.au/>.

- House of Representatives Standing Committee on Industry, Innovation, Science and Resources. (2020, December 7). *From rubbish to resources: Building a circular economy*. Parliament of Australia. Analysis & Policy Observatory (APO). <https://apo.org.au/node/309956>.
- Hudson, B., Hunter, D., & Peckham, S. (2019). Policy failure and the policy-implementation gap: Can policy support programs help? *Policy Design and Practice*, 2(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2018.1540378>.
- Kay, A. (2011). Evidence-based policymaking: The elusive search for rational public administration. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 70(3), 236–245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2011.00728.x>.
- National Association of Charitable Recycling Organisations. (2020). *National textiles reuse policy: Briefing paper*. <https://www.charitablerecycling.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/National-Textiles-Reuse-Policy-Recommendation-2020.pdf>.
- National Retail Association. (2022, August 17). *National Waste Policy Action Plan: Waste management Australia*. <https://www.nra.net.au/policy-advocacy/sustainability-environment/national-waste-policy/>.
- Queensland University of Technology Design Lab. (2021, May 26). *National clothing and textile waste roundtable & exhibition*. <https://research.qut.edu.au/designlab/2021/06/16/national-clothing-and-textile-waste-roundtable-exhibition/>.
- Raturier, S. (2022, August 29). Everything you need to know about waste in the fashion industry. *Good On You*. <https://goodonyou.eco/waste-luxury-fashion/>.
- Ross, A., & Dovers, S. (2008). Making the harder yards: Environmental policy integration in Australia. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 67(3), 245–260. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2008.00585.x>.
- Schneider, A. L., & Ingram, H. (2017). The pragmatic policy analyst. In *Renascent pragmatism* (pp. 156–179). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315244525-7>
- Stone, D. A. (1989). Causal stories and the formation of policy agendas. *Political Science Quarterly*, 104(2), 281–300. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2151585>
- Stone, D. A. (2002). *Policy paradox: The art of political decision making* (Rev. ed.). W. W. Norton.